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Research Article

**IN SILICO AND IN VITRO ANTI-INFLAMMATORY
ACTIVITY OF ETHANOLIC LEAF EXTRACT OF
BIOPHYTUM SENSITIVUM**Harithahareendran.G^{*1}, Abhishek B Vijayan^{*1}, Arya.S.S^{*1},Mrs. Anusree S², Mrs. Aswathy. S.S³, Dr. Kiran K J⁴, Dr. Prasobh GR⁵

¹B Pharm Students, Sree Krishna College of Pharmacy and Research Centre Parassala, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, India. ²Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Sree Krishna College of Pharmacy and Research Centre Parassala, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, India., ³Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Sree Krishna College of Pharmacy and Research Centre Parassala, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, India. ⁴Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Sree Krishna College of Pharmacy and Research Centre Parassala, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, India., ⁵Principal, Sree Krishna College of Pharmacy and Research Centre Parassala, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, India.

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Abstract:

The present study aimed to evaluate the anti-inflammatory potential of ethanolic extract of Biophytum sensitivum leaves using in silico and in vitro methods. Preliminary phytochemical screening indicated the presence of flavonoids, phenolic compounds, essential oils, saponins. In silico studies are carried out using molecular docking studies, ligand molecule amentoflavone shows binding affinity with IC7V and 1YPU receptors respectively. The extract inhibits protein denaturation, cyclooxygenase, lipoxygenase. In this study, the results demonstrated that the ethanolic extract of Biophytum sensitivum leaves possess moderate anti-inflammatory activity.

Keywords: Anti- inflammatory activity, Biophytum sensitivum, Docking studies, In vitro studies.

Corresponding author:Harithahareendran.G- haritha695141@gmail.comAbhishek. B. Vijayan- abhishekbvijayan@gmail.comArya. S. S- arya2001ss@gmail.com

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INTRODUCTION:

diseases with inflammatory etiology or pathology cases are increase around the globe.[1] these inflammatory diseases, due to the different systems in our body, are very difficult to treat. inflammation is an important process in the human immune system in response to various harmful stimuli and is highly regulated to restrict its action to the appropriate spatial and temporal circumstances. [2,3] inflammation is a host defense mechanism of the body. it is an essential immune response that allows the body to survive during infection or contamination. inflammation most normally considered as a pathological process can be beneficial in fight against deleterious infection or injury.[4]

biophytum sensitivum is a medicinal plant belongs to the family oxalidaceae distributed in tropical asia, africa and philippines. it is found in the wetlands of tropical india . it is commonly known as life plant which is a mesophytic under- shrub grows in shade of trees. flower of this plant is considered as one of the ten sacred plant which are called as “dashapushpam” in traditional culture of kerala.[5] this plant shows an immense nutritional and medicinal benefits. traditional practices of the plant are bitter, expectorant, stimulant, and tonic in ayurveda. and it is recommended for the treatment of asthma, stomach-ache, insomnia, convulsions, cramps, chest pain, convulsions and also for chronic skin disease. *b. sensitivum* is one of the plants which is used against snake envenomation. the plant contains rich source of tannins, phenolic compounds and polyphenolic compounds, essential oil, saponins.[6] molecular docking studies is a computational technique which predicts the affinity of ligands to receptor proteins.

this is the method of bioinformatic modelling for predicting the interactions between receptor and studied molecules. through this docking studies the potential generation of stable adducts by the aid of an optimized docking conformation.[7] *in silico* models encodes and test hypothesis about various underlying mechanisms about cell function, pathophysiology and pathogenesis of diseases.[8] docking based virtual approach was performed mainly by the aid of auto dock vina implicated in the pyrx 0.8 tools and pymol software is used for 3d visualizing of macromolecules. pymol is one of the most popular tools for preparing high resolution images of macromolecules.

protein denaturation result in the production of auto-antigens in inflammatory disorders such as rheumatoid arthritis. by the inhibition of protein denaturation, inflammatory activity can also be inhibited. this alters the unique 3d conformation of the protein molecules without causing concomitant cleavage of bond which leads to the temporary or permanent loss of activity.

inflammation is a protective response that is initiated either after injury, physical and chemical damage, or infection by microorganisms, but persistent inflammation may cause chronic diseases. inflammation is caused by the body release of hormone-like substances called prostaglandins (pgs) and leukotrienes (lts). these inflammatory inducing agents are produced from arachidonic acid (aa) by the enzymes cyclooxygenase (cox) and lipoxigenase (lox). cox is the first enzyme in the pathway for producing pg and thromboxane (tx) from arachidonic acid.

Figure No.1: *Biophytum sensitivum*

MATERIALS AND METHODS:**Collection and authentication of plant material:**

The whole plant of *Biophytum sensitivum* is collected from Thiruvananthapuram in the month of April. The plant material was identified and authenticated from Department of Botany, Nesamony Memorial Christian College, Marthandam.

Preparation of plant material:

The sample was washed thoroughly with fresh water and air dried at room temperature under shade for 15 days and pulverized into coarse powder by the aid of mechanical grinder. The powder material was stored in airtight container.

Preparation of plant extract [9]:

50g of pulverized powder was extracted by maceration technique with 1000 ml of 75% ethanol. The mixture was subjected continuous shaking at room temperature. After 1 week the extract was strained with muslin cloth and the crude extract was concentrated to dryness under reduced pressure and controlled temperature and stored in airtight container for further use.

The percentage yield of extract was calculated using the formula;

$$\text{Percentage yield} = \frac{W_2}{W_1} \times 100$$

Where,

W1 – weight in grams of dried plant material
W2 – weight in grams of extract obtained

Preliminary Phytochemical Screening[10][11]

Qualitative phytochemical screening was carried out for flavonoids, phenolic compounds, saponins and essential oils using standard procedures.

In silico* molecular docking studies[12]:*Step 1: Ligand preparation**

Chemical structure of the ligand amentoflavone was

The percentage inhibition of protein denaturation was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Percentage of inhibition} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of control} - \text{Absorbance of test sample}}{\text{Absorbance of control}} \times 100$$

Cyclooxygenase (COX) Assay[15] Procedure:**Cell lines:**

RAW 264.7 cell line was purchased from NCCS, Pune and was maintained in Dulbecco's modified eagles' media (Himedia, India) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (Himedia, India) and grown to confluence at 37°C at 5% CO₂ in a CO₂ incubator.

Pre-processing:

RAW 264.7 cells were grown to 60% confluence followed by activation with 1 ml lipopolysaccharide

obtained from the chemistry databases PubChem. Chemical structures of the compounds are downloaded in 3D format and converted to sdf format. Finally, the input format prepared as pdb ligand format and can be visualized in open babel.

Step 2: Protein preparation

Target molecules such as human arachidonate lipoxygenase and human cyclooxygenase COX 2 can be determined by literature survey and respective PDB files such as 1C7V, 1YPU were downloaded from protein data bank.

Step 3: Protein processing

Protein structure processing is done by removal of water molecules, hydrogens, heteroatoms and bound ligand if any.

Step 4: Docking analysis

Docking analysis was done by Auto dock Vina Program in PyRx software. For this purpose, installed Auto dock tools

(Python 2.7.1, MGL tools 1.5.4 and Open babel) and PyRx. Installed Auto dock tools (Python 2.7.1, MGL tools 1.5.4 and Open babel) and PyRx.

Step 5: Molecular visualization

PyMOL is software used for the protein preparation and molecular visualization. It produces high quality 3D images of protein.

In vitro* study anti-inflammatory activity:*Protein denaturation inhibition assay[13][14] Procedure:**

The reaction mixture (0.5 ml) consisted of 0.4 ml bovine serum albumin (3% aqueous solution) and varying concentrations of test sample. The samples were incubated at 37°C for 20 min and 2.5ml phosphate buffered saline (pH 6.3) was added to each tube and then heated at 80°C for 10 min. The absorbance was measured using spectrophotometer at 660nm.

(LPS) (1 µg/ml). LPS stimulated RAW cells were exposed with different concentration of test sample solution and the standard provided. The plates were incubated for 24 hours. After incubation the anti-inflammatory assays were performed using the cell lysate.

Cell lysate preparation:

- Trypsinize and harvest RAW cells (activated by LPS and treated with standard diclofenac as well as the test compound at different concentrations)

- and centrifuge 3000 rpm for 2 min.
- Resuspend the pellet in Tris HCL buffer pH8.0
- Freeze the cells at -20° C for 20 minutes
- Keep the cells at 65° C for 5 minutes
- Immediately transfer to -20° C for 10 minute
- Cool to room temperature
- Centrifuge at 1200 rpm for 2 minutes
- Take supernatant which is the cell lysate for further analysis.

The COX activity was assayed by the method of Walker and Gierse with slight modifications. The cell lysate in Tris- HCl buffer (pH 8) was incubated with glutathione 5 Mm/L, and Haemoglobin 20 µg/L for 1 minute at 25°C. The reaction was initiated by the addition of arachidonic acid 200 Mm/L and terminated after 20 minutes of incubation at 37°C, by the addition of 10% trichloroacetic acid in 1 N hydrochloric acid. After the centrifugal separation and the addition of 1% thiobarbiturate, COX activity was determined by reading absorbance at 632 nm.

Cyclooxygenase (COX) Assay:

Percentage inhibition of the enzyme was calculated as,

$$\text{Percentage of inhibition} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of control} - \text{Absorbance of sample}}{\text{Absorbance of control}} \times 100$$

Lipoxygenase (LOX) Assay[16]:

Procedure:

RAW 264.7 cell line was used for the study purpose. The determination of 5-LOX activity was as per Axelrod et al.(1981). Briefly, the reaction mixture (2 ml final volume) contained Tris- HCl buffer (pH 7.4), 50 ml of cell lysate, and sodium linoleate (200 ml; 10mg/ml). The LOX activity was monitored as difference in absorbance at 234 nm, which reflects the formation of 5- hydroxy eicosatetraenoic acid from linoleate.

Percentage inhibition of the enzyme will be calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Percentage of inhibition} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of control} - \text{Absorbance of sample}}{\text{Absorbance of control}} \times 100$$

RESULT:

Percentage yield:

Table No 1: Percentage yield of Leaf extract of *Biophytum sensitivum*

NAME OF THE PLANT	PLANT PARTS USED	METHOD OF EXTRACTION	SOLVENT USED FOR EXTRACTION	PERCENTAGE YIELD (%w/w)
<i>Biophytum sensitivum</i>	Leaf	Maceration	Ethanol	10 % w/w

Preliminary phytochemical screening:

Table No 2: Summary of preliminary phytochemical screening of ethanolic leaf extract of *Biophytum sensitivum*

SL. NO.	NAME OF THE CONSTITUENTS	NAME OF THE TEST	ELEBS
1.	Flavonoids	Lead acetate test	+
		Alkaline reagent test	+
		Ferric chloride test	+
		Ammonia test	+
		Sulphuric acid test	+
2.	Saponins	Foam test	+
3.	Essential oils	Solubility test	+
4.	Phenols	Ferric chloride test	+
		Iodine test	+
		Gelatin test	+
		Potassium dichromate test	+

ELEBS- Ethanolic leaf extract of *Biophytum sensitivum*

(+) - Positive
 (-) - Negative

In silico docking study of *Biophytum sensitivum*:

In silico docking studies facilitates interactions among the components in a system and mathematical and computed models are established and predict the interaction between ligand and target molecules. From various literature reviews founded that *Biophytum sensitivum* leaves possess bi-flavones i.e. amentoflavone which has the ability to produce anti-inflammatory activities. Amentoflavone shows binding affinity with 1C7V, 1YPU receptors.

Figure No 2: Docking image of amentoflavone with receptor 1C7V

Figure No 3: Docking image of amentoflavone with receptor 1YPU

Table No 3: Hydrogen bond interaction and binding affinity of Amentoflavone with receptors

RECEPTOR	NUMBER OF HYDROGEN BOND INTERACTIONS	BINDING AFFINITY (KCAL/MOL)
1C7V	5	-8.111
1YPU	1	-7.844

***In vitro* study of *Biophytum sensitivum*:**

Protein Denaturation Inhibition Assay:

The inhibitory rate of protein denaturation for ethanolic leaf extract of *Biophytum sensitivum* increased gradually with concentration. In this study ethanolic leaf extract of *Biophytum sensitivum* showed maximum inhibition, 56.68% at 100 µg/ml. Diclofenac, a standard anti-inflammatory drug showed the maximum inhibition, 84.12% at the concentration of 100 µg/ml. The percentage inhibition value at different concentration is given in Table No. 4

Table No 4: Effect of Ethanolic leaf extract of *Biophytum sensitivum* in Protein Denaturation Inhibition Assay

TREATMENT	CONCENTRATION (µg/ml)	ABSORBANCE	PERCENTAGE INHIBITION
CONTROL	-	0.787	-
ELEBS	6.25	0.682	7.08
	12.5	0.599	18.39
	25	0.547	25.48
	50	0.485	33.92
	100	0.318	56.68
DICLOFENAC	6.25	0.725	7.88
	12.5	0.661	16.01

ELEBS - Ethanolic Leaf Extract of *Biophytum sensitivum*

Figure No 4: Effect of ethanolic leaf extract of *Biophytum sensitivum* in Protein Denaturation Inhibition Assay

Cyclooxygenase (COX) Assay:

At increasing concentrations, ethanolic extract of leaf of *Biophytum sensitivum* efficiently inhibited the COX enzymes. Thus, the sample studied exhibited cyclooxygenase (COX) activity i.e. the sample has anti-inflammatory property. This is an indication that the test sample has the potential to be developed as non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs). The result shows maximum COX inhibitory efficacy at concentration 100 µg/ml in comparison with standard. The IC₅₀ value of COX inhibition was found to be 103.06 µg/ml. The percentage inhibition value at different concentration is given in Table No. 5

Table No 5: Effect of Ethanolic leaf extract of *Biophytum sensitivum* in Cyclooxygenase (COX) Assay

TREATMENT	CONCENTRATION (µg/ ml)	ABSORBANCE	PERCENTAGE INHIBITION
CONTROL	-	0.728	-
DICLOFENAC	6.25	0.684	10.81
	12.5	0.627	21.16
	25	0.575	35.18
	50	0.486	49.93
	100	0.395	70.82
ELEBS	6.25	0.649	6.00
	12.5	0.574	13.83
	25	0.472	20.93
	50	0.364	33.26
	100	0.212	45.76

ELEBS - Ethanolic Leaf Extract of *Biophytum sensitivum*

Figure No 5: Comparison of the effect of ethanolic leaf extract of *Biophytum sensitivum* with diclofenac in Cyclooxygenase (COX) Assay

Lipoxygenase (LOX) Assay:

At increasing concentrations, ethanolic extract of leaf of *Biophytum sensitivum* efficiently inhibited the LOX enzymes. Thus, the sample studied exhibited lipoxygenase inhibitory activity i.e. the sample has anti-inflammatory property. This is an indication that the test sample has the potential to be developed as non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs). The result shows LOX inhibition action have maximum efficacy at the concentration 100 µg/ml. The IC₅₀ value of LOX inhibition was found to be 115.68 µg/ml. The percentage inhibition value at different concentration is given in Table No. 6

Table no 6: Effect of Ethanolic leaf extract of *Biophytum sensitivum* in Lipoxygenase (LOX) Assay

TREATMENT	CONCENTRATION (µg/ ml)	ABSORBANCE	PERCENTAGE INHIBITION
CONTROL	-	0.565	-
DICLOFENAC	6.25	0.525	7.13
	12.5	0.483	14.62
	25	0.395	30.13
	50	0.295	47.88
ELEBS	100	0.176	68.93
	6.25	0.546	3.42
	12.5	0.498	11.97
	25	0.451	20.22
	50	0.395	30.19
	100	0.332	41.21

ELEBS - Ethanolic Leaf Extract of *Biophytum sensitivum*

Figure No 6: Comparison of the effect of ethanolic leaf extract of *Biophytum sensitivum* with diclofenac in Lipoxygenase (LOX) Assay

DISCUSSION:

Biophytum sensitivum has a unique position in Ayurveda. *Biophytum sensitivum* belongs to the family Oxalidaceae distributed in Tropical Asia, Africa and the Philippines. It is found in the wetlands of tropical India. It is commonly known as Life plant which is a mesophytic under- shrub grows in shade of trees. The plant has been investigated for various pharmacological including analgesic, anti-pyretic, anti-tumor, anti-bacterial, antihypertensive, antidiabetic, antioxidant, chemoprotective,

radioprotective, anti-asthmatic, anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory activities. The plant contains rich source of phenolic and polyphenolic compounds, saponins, tannins, essential oil, polysaccharides, and pectin. Study was conducted in the ethanolic leaf extract of *Biophytum sensitivum* on the basis of *Biophytum sensitivum* leaf extract have anti-inflammatory action due to the presence of flavonoids.

The whole plant of *Biophytum sensitivum* is collected

from Thiruvananthapuram in the month of April. The plant material was identified and authenticated from Department of Botany, Nesamony Memorial Christian College, Marthandam. Then the sample was washed thoroughly with fresh water and air dried at room temperature under shade for 15 days and pulverized by the aid of a mechanical grinder and the powder material was stored in airtight container. For the preparation of the ethanolic extract of 50g of pulverized powder is extracted with 1000ml of 75% ethanol. The mixture was subjected continuous shaking at room temperature. The extract was concentrated to dryness under reduced pressure and controlled temperature and stored in airtight container for further use. The percentage yield of ethanolic leaf extract of leaf was found to be 10% w/w.

The freshly prepared ethanolic leaf extract of *Biophytum sensitivum* were subjected to phytochemical screening test for the detection of various active constituents. The phytochemical analysis of leaf extract of *Biophytum sensitivum* showed the presence of phenol, flavonoid, saponins and fixed oils. From the most of studies, it is indicated that flavonoids possess anti-inflammatory activity.

In silico molecular docking studies are used to predicts the affinity of ligands to receptor proteins. Docking is economical, reliable, and time saving method for the screening of larger set of lead molecule. Docking based virtual approach was performed mainly by the aid of Auto dock VINA implicated in the PyRx 0.8 tools and PyMOL software is used for 3D visualizing of macromolecules. From the review of literature, it was found that bi-flavone amentoflavone has anti-inflammatory activity. So amentoflavone was taken as ligand and docking was performed with many receptors which possess significant role in inflammation. Amentoflavone expresses stronger binding affinity with selected receptor such as 1C7V, 1YPU. Thus, the docking study indicates that amentoflavone possess anti-inflammatory activity.

Inflammation occurs due to tissue injury and the denaturation of intracellular chemical substances and protein components within cells. Therefore, it seems that a substance's potential for anti-inflammatory effect is determined by its capacity to suppress protein denaturation. As a part of the current investigation the ability of ethanolic leaf extracts to inhibits protein denaturation was studied at different concentration 6.25, 12.5, 25, 50, 100µg/ml. The results revealed that extracts produce concentration dependent

activity. According to reports, NSAIDS like diclofenac, which are used to treat inflammation, inhibit protein denaturation. The extract shown moderate reduction in protein denaturation when compared to standard diclofenac in protein denaturation inhibition assay. The secondary metabolites such as phenolics and flavonoids in the extracts might be responsible for the observed activity.

The enzymes implicated in the arachidonic pathway that causes inflammation are COX and LOX. The COX enzyme is crucial to the cyclooxygenase process of inflammation. It is a membrane-bound glycoprotein that is present in cells that generate prostanoids. It manifests as COX-1 and COX-2, two identical COX forms that have distinct intracellular sites and substrate and inhibitor selectivity. Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are COX inhibitors, but they also inhibit COX-1, which is problematic because COX-1 is required for a number of physiological processes. Therefore, there is a particular need for agents that selectively inhibit COX-2 without harming COX-1. LOX enzymes have significant roles to play key role in asthma, inflammation, and angiogenesis. In the present investigation, various concentrations of ethanolic leaf extract of *Biophytum sensitivum* were analysed for cyclooxygenase and 5-lipoxygenase inhibitory activity using *in vitro* assay models. The results revealed that the extract show inhibition of cyclooxygenase and 5-lipoxygenase in a dose dependent manner as compared with standard diclofenac and this inhibition might be attributed to the anti-inflammatory potential of the extracts. Various investigation shown that different polyphenols and flavonoids modulate the activity of arachidonic acid metabolizing enzymes such as COX and LOX. COX and LOX are responsible for the production of metabolites with capacity to increase the oxidative lesion in tissues. Some polyphenols and flavonoids have properties to inhibit the activities of COX and LOX.

Hence the presence of these phytochemical constituents in the ethanolic extract of *Biophytum sensitivum* may contribute anti-inflammatory activities. The present study explores the phytochemical constituents of ethanolic extracts of *Biophytum sensitivum* leaves and evaluate its anti-inflammatory activity based on the evidences from the ethnomedicinal studies of the plant.

CONCLUSION:

The present study was done to evaluate the *in vitro* and *in silico* anti-inflammatory activity of ethanolic

leaf extract of *Biophytum sensitivum*, seen in tropical regions which possess immense nutritional and medicinal benefits. The inhibitory action of ethanolic leaf extract of *Biophytum sensitivum* increases gradually with the concentration as a dose dependent manner. This is an indication that plant possess anti-inflammatory activity because of the presence active constituents mainly flavonoids i.e. amentoflavone and minute amount of cupressuflavone. These findings suggest that *Biophytum sensitivum* may warranting further clinical studies to explore its anti-inflammatory potential.

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